

Research

Preparation and application of a new composite COD remover

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Accepted: 10 December, 2020; **Online:** 19 December, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4362302>

Abstract: The purpose of this study is the preparation of a new category, high degradable efficiency, and low-cost composite COD remover. The composite COD remover was made by double oxidants composition method and coupling oxidants and flocculants composition method in a precise proportion. The best prepared composite COD remover was the R-1 [potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) and sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$)] composite COD remover at the pH of 6, reaction temperature 40°C, and 30 minutes reaction time. The maximum removal rate of chemical oxygen demand (COD) was 97.3 %. The best ratio of the new composite COD remover was 2:1. Compared with the commercial COD remover, the removal rate of COD increased by more than 16% and the treatment cost of wastewater decreased by more than 6%. Therefore, the new composite COD remover from this experimental study had great reaction performance, cost-effective and obvious economic and environmental benefits.

Keywords: Composite COD remover; Composition method; Oxidants; Flocculants; Chemical oxygen demand.

1. Introduction

Chemical oxygen demand (COD) is a fundamental investigation for approaching the industrial effluents and wastewater quality before discharging into the environment. Moreover, chemical oxygen demand (COD) of the wastewater is a rapid and cheap means to determine the concentration of organics fractions extant in the wastewater (Hammer, 1986; Sheth, Italia, Sheth, & Italia; Stone, 2011). Distinctive treatment method is chosen depending on the wastewater characteristics and the objectives of treatment. A thorough arrangement of wastewater treatment

may involve coagulation and precipitation method (iron and aluminium salt, organic coagulant), the combination of a number of physical (filtration technologies, adsorption, membrane using technologies, etc.), chemical (chemical oxidation and advanced oxidation, chemical coagulation, chemical precipitation, electrochemical treatment methods, disinfection, etc.) and biological (bioreactor, continuous batch reactor, etc.) techniques (Ben Rebah & Siddeeg, 2017). The rapid growth of industrialization causes pollution problems especially water bodies of the environment (Babu, 2019). Industrial wastewater is one of the critical pollution resources in water environment pollution (Hanchang, 2009). Chemical oxygen demand (COD) may not reach the relevant national discharge standards after doing the biological treatment for some industrial wastewater with poor biodegradability. The biological treatment process is not accomplished to separate complex organic compounds from wastewater. Therefore, other treatment methods such as physical treatment and/or chemical oxidation treatment methods are used to treat organic industrial wastewater. Numerous investigations have been targeted on experiments to promote relevant technological explanations by coupling physical and chemical treatment processes. Hence, the combination of chemical oxidation and flocculation has been successfully consumed for the highly polluted industrial wastewater treatment. Flocculation process lowers the original concentration of organic pollutants in the wastewater and consequently the requirements of chemical oxidants for the treatment process and reducing the total treatment cost (Gema Pliego, Zazo, Blasco, Casas, & Rodriguez, 2012; G. Pliego et al., 2014; Rizzo, 2011). The traditional chemicals and flocculants can combine with reverse osmosis and other treatment technologies to get good treatment results. As a result of high treatment costs, prolonged treatment time and complicated operating procedures, this process is difficult to incorporate with some treatment technology in the practical engineering process. Hence, the direct addition of oxidants or flocculants to the wastewater sample for the reduction of COD may be a simple and effective technique (Kaczur & Cawlfild, 2000; Meng et al., 2019). A wide variety of oxidants and flocculants can be utilized for water and wastewater treatment. The most common used oxidants and flocculants are sodium hypochlorite, chlorine dioxide, ozone, chlorine, ferric sulphate, ferric chloride, and aluminium sulphate. Potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) is a strong oxidant in the entire range of pH and possesses unique properties among other chemical reagents (Jia-Qian & Barry, 2002; J.-Q. Jiang, Lloyd, & Grigore, 2001; J.-Q. Jiang, Wang, & Panagouloupoulos, 2005; Jia Qian Jiang, Wang, & Panagouloupoulos, 2006; Virender K. Sharma, 2002). Several examinations have been performed in utilizing

potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) as beneficial alternative disinfection to chlorine for the disinfection of water and as favourable oxidants and coagulants in water and wastewater treatment (Greville & Environmental, 1997; Jun & Wei, 2002; Schink & Waite, 1980). The main problem of this research was the reduction of chemical oxygen demand (COD) which is difficult to remove and degrade from organic industrial wastewater. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to the preparation of a new category, high degradable efficiency, and low-cost composite COD remover by composition with oxidants and flocculants.

In this work of study, the new composite COD remover with high degradable efficiency produced from the basis of the oxidant potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) and activated it with other strong oxidants and flocculants by using sodium hypochlorite ($NaOCl$), sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$), calcium hypochlorite [$Ca(ClO)_2$], poly-ferric sulfate (PFS) and poly-aluminium ferric silicate (PSAF). The new composite COD remover can effectively degrade and remove organic pollutants in the organic industrial wastewater. The comparable performance of the new composite COD remover showed good results. The new composite COD remover has greater degradable efficiency than the commonly used commercial COD remover. Therefore, the new composite COD remover has distinct economic and environmental benefits.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Raw Wastewater

The raw wastewater sample used in this research was taken from the wastewater tank of Hubei Nongchang Pesticides Chemicals Company Limited, Yangxin City, Hubei Province, Wuhan, P.R. China. The main components of this wastewater sample were organic phosphorus, heterocyclic compounds, and other organic pollutants. The initial parameters of the wastewater sample were firstly analyzed. The initial concentration for chemical oxygen demand (COD) of this wastewater sample was 1100 mg/L. The physiochemical characteristics of raw wastewater sample are shown in Table (1).

Table 1 Physiochemical characteristics of organic industrial wastewater sample

Sr. No.	Parameters	Range (mg/L)
1.	COD (Chemical Oxygen Demand)	1100
2.	pH	6 ~ 9
3.	SS (Suspended Solid)	220
4.	Ammonia/Nitrogen	830
5.	TP (Total Phosphorus)	15
6.	Colour	Dark yellow
7.	Odour	Objectionable
8.	Turbidity (NTU)	17~25

2.2 Main Reagents

The main reagents used in this experiment were potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4), sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$), sodium hypochlorite ($NaOCl$), calcium hypochlorite [$Ca(OCl)_2$], poly-ferric sulfate (PFS) and poly-aluminium ferric silicate (PSAF). All the chemicals used in this work were analytical grade.

2.3 Main Equipments

Spectrophotometer (HACH-DR, Shanghai Shangguo instrument Technology Co., Ltd) was used to measure absorbency of wastewater sample that calculate the values of COD. Laboratory pH meter (PHS-3G, Youlebo Technology Co., Ltd) was used to measure the pH of wastewater sample. Electronic analytical balance (YP 1002, Shanghai Chuyan Laboratory Equipment Co., Ltd); Electric-heated thermostatic water bath (HHS-26, Shanghai Dongxing Building Materials and Experimental Equipment Co., Ltd); COD Digestion system equipment (HACH-DR 200, Shanghai Broad Instrument Technology Co., Ltd); Turbidity meter (WGZ-1B, Shanghai Xinrui Instruments and Equipments Co., Ltd.) and Colorimeter (HZW-3A, Xiamen Fujian Survey Instruments and Equipment Co., Ltd.) were also used in this research.

2.4 Experimental Procedures

2.4.1 Experimental procedure for common oxidants and flocculants on COD removal rate

About 500 ml of wastewater samples were taken by measuring cylinder and added into the beakers. The initial pH value of the wastewater sample was 6.8. Then the certain amounts of different common oxidants were separately added to the raw wastewater sample. After adding the oxidants, the mixture was mixed and stirred rapidly by 150 rpm/min for 15 minutes and then slowly by 60 rpm/min for 10 minutes with a magnetic stirrer. The reaction was conducted at room temperature and the pH of the raw wastewater was maintained. The mixture was settled for 30 minutes without disturbed after stirring process. The supernatant liquid was filtered and taken for the determination of chemical oxygen demand (COD). The best oxidant for the COD removal was chosen for the formulation of new COD remover by composition methods. The above procedure was repeated for the common commercial flocculants.

2.4.2 Experimental procedure for composite COD removers

According to the results from the above experimental procedure, the new composite COD removers were made by the composition of oxidants and flocculants. About 500 ml of wastewater sample was taken by measuring cylinder and added into the separate beakers. A certain amounts of the prepared composite COD removers with various ratios were added separately into the beakers. The reaction temperature was kept at 40°C and the pH of the raw wastewater sample was maintained. The mixture of COD removers and wastewater sample was stirred with magnetic stirrer. The agitation speed was kept 150 rpm/min for 15 minutes and then 60 rpm/min for 10 minutes. The mixture of wastewater samples was left for 30 minutes after the stirring process completed. Then, the supernatant liquid of wastewater sample was taken and determined the concentration of chemical oxygen demand (COD).

The above procedure was repeated for other set of experimental conditions after the optimum dosage and ratio of the COD remover was determined. The effect of COD removal was determined by double oxidants composition and coupling oxidant and flocculants composition methods. The best ratio of the each new composite COD remover was selected and the above experimental process was repeated on the different pH condition (pH 4 to pH 10) as adjusted by sulphuric acid and sodium hydroxide solution, the reaction time (10 minutes to 60 minutes), and

the different temperature range (25°C, 40°C, 50°C, 60°C and 70°C.). The comparison process of the new composite COD remover and commercial COD remover was also carried out under this experimental conditions.

2.5 Experimental Methods

2.5.1 Determination of Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD)

The concentration of chemical oxygen demand (COD) in the wastewater sample was determined by the rapid digestion method. In this experiment, the wastewater sample was mixed with potassium dichromate under acidic conditions and digested at 150°C for two hours. After the digestion process, the concentration of chemical oxygen demand (COD) in the digested solution has a linear relationship with the absorbance. The absorbance of the wastewater sample was measured by a spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 620 nm. The calculation method of rate of chemical oxygen demand (COD) removal from the wastewater sample is as follows:

$$\text{Rate of COD removal (\%)} = \frac{A - B}{A} \times 100\%$$

where A was concentration of COD before treatment and B was concentration of COD after treatment.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Effect of common oxidants and flocculants on COD removal rate

Figure (1) shows the percentage of chemical oxygen demand (COD) reduction for different traditional oxidants at different dosages. For this experiment, the dosages of different oxidants were set as 0 g, 0.4 g, 0.6 g, 0.8 g, 1.0 g, 1.2 g, 1.4 g, 1.6 g, 1.8 g, and 2.0 g/L. This experiment was carried out for the degradation effect of traditional oxidants on the raw wastewater sample. In this experiment, we used potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4), sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$), sodium hypochlorite ($NaOCl$), and calcium hypochlorite [$Ca(OCl)_2$]. The experimental results showed that the addition of only oxidant had a poor removal efficiency of COD from the raw wastewater sample. According to the results, potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) has a good COD removal effect among other oxidants. The highest removal rate of COD was 50.9 % by using the dosage of 1.6 g of potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4). Potassium ferrate has both oxidation and flocculation effect.

Moreover, it has shown high agreement as a multi-function wastewater treatment chemical for oxidation, disinfection and coagulation/flocculation process. A great oxidation efficiency of ferrate (VI) in the reduction of COD can be noted to the great redox potential and possesses the strongest oxidation efficiency among all other oxidants (Jia-Qian & Barry, 2002; Jia Qian Jiang et al., 2006; Virender K Sharma, Kazama, Jiangyong, & Ray, 2005). The removal efficiency of potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) was gradually increased by 22.5 % to 50.9 % between the dosage 0.4 g and 1.6 g. But the removal rate was hardly decreased at the dosage 1 g. It was found that potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) effectively reacted with the pollutants that included in the organic wastewater sample. When the 1.6 g of sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$) added to the wastewater sample, the percentage of COD removal rate reached 46.3 %. Sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$) also gives good removal action on the wastewater sample. But the reaction efficiency for the wastewater treatment was less than potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4). The maximum percentage of COD removal rates for sodium hypochlorite ($NaOCl$) and calcium hypochlorite [$Ca(OCl)_2$] were 41.7 % and 33.2 % at the dosage 1.8 g and 1.4 g respectively. Their reaction efficiencies were weak for the removal of COD from the using raw pesticide wastewater sample. It was apparently seen from the experimental results that potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) has greater removal efficiency among other oxidants.

Figure (2) shows the effect of common flocculants on the COD removal rate of the raw wastewater sample. Poly-ferric sulfate (PFS) and poly-aluminium ferric silicate (PSAF) were used for this experiment. PFS and PSAF are kind of inorganic composite polymer flocculants which is widely used in the water and wastewater treatment. Flocculation process lowers the original concentration of organic pollutants in the wastewater sample and consequently the requirements of chemical oxidants for the treatment process (Duan & Gregory, 2003; Leiknes, 2009). As can be seen from figure (2), PFS and PSAF has the poor removal effect on the raw wastewater sample. The removal effect was gradually increased with the increase dosages of PFS and PSAF. The maximum removal rate for PFS and PSAF was 30.7 % and 30.1 % at the dosage of 0.5 g/L. The flocculants greatly reduced the turbidity of the wastewater sample. The addition of only flocculants make the insoluble suspended particles in the wastewater sample accumulate larger and settled down rapidly. Therefore, it cannot degrade and reduce the chemical oxygen demand (COD) effectively in the treatment.

Figure 1 Effect of COD reduction for different common oxidants at different dosages

Figure 2 Effect of COD reduction for common flocculants at different dosages

Based on the result of figure (1) and (2), it was observed that the using of only one oxidant and flocculants cannot effectively degrade and reduce the organic pollutants and the chemical oxygen demand (COD) from organic industrial wastewater sample for the treatment. The percentage reduction of chemical oxygen demand cannot reach to the acceptable standard limit. Moreover, the treatment cost and reaction time was high when the only one oxidant and flocculants used in the treatment. Therefore, the composite COD remover was produced for the significance of great reaction performance, economic and environmental benefits.

3.2 Effect of composition of double oxidants on the rate of COD removal

From the above experimental results, the new composite COD remover was produced from the basis of potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) by double oxidants composition and coupling oxidant and flocculants composition methods. Figure (3) shows the composition effect of double oxidants on the rate of COD removal. In this experiment, the dosage of potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) was set as 1.2 g, 1.4 g, 1.6 g, 1.8 g, 2.0 g and 2.4 g/L for each experiment respectively. The dosage of sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$), sodium hypochlorite ($NaOCl$) and calcium hypochlorite [$Ca(OCl)_2$] were prepared 0.2 g, 0.5 g, 0.8 g, 1.1 g, 1.4 g, 1.7 g, and 2.0 g/L respectively. The reaction was carried out at 40°C and the reaction pH of raw wastewater was maintained. When the dosage of potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) was set as 1.2g/L, the maximum removal rate of COD for sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$) was 52.6 % at 1.4 g/L, sodium hypochlorite ($NaOCl$) was 53.5 % at 1.1 g/L and calcium hypochlorite [$Ca(OCl)_2$] was 50.7% at 1.7 g/L respectively as seen from figure 3(a). For the reaction with sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$), the removal rate was gradually increased by 18.9 % to 40.8 % between the dosages of 0.2 g/L to 0.8 g/L. The removal rate was decreased by the increase dosage of sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$) after getting the maximum removal rate. The removal rate of COD was gradually increased between the dosages of 0.2 g/L to 1.1 g/L of sodium hypochlorite ($NaOCl$). As the results shown in figure 3(b), when the dosage of potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) was set as 1.4 g/L, the maximum removal rate of COD for sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$) was 65% at 1.1 g/L, sodium hypochlorite ($NaOCl$) was 62.5 % at 1.4 g/L and calcium hypochlorite [$Ca(OCl)_2$] was 64.5 % at 1.4 g/L respectively.

According to the results shown in figure 3(c), when the dosage of potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) was set as 1.6 g/L, the maximum removal rate of COD for sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$) was 97.3% at 0.8 g/L, sodium hypochlorite ($NaOCl$) was 72.2 % at 1.7 g/L and calcium hypochlorite [$Ca(OCl)_2$] was 65.6% at 0.8 g/L respectively. The results of figure 3(c) apparently showed that sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$) had a better removal efficiency than the other oxidants and had a great composition effect with potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4). The composition of double oxidants can effectively degrade and reduce the chemical oxygen demand (COD) in the using wastewater sample. The dosage of potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) increased to set as 1.8 g/L. The maximum removal rate of COD for sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$) was 90.8% at 2.0 g/L, sodium hypochlorite ($NaOCl$) was 84.5 % at 0.8 g/L and calcium hypochlorite [$Ca(OCl)_2$] was 81% at 1.1 g/L

respectively. The results were shown in figure 3(d). When the dosage of potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) was set as 2.0 g/L, the maximum removal rate of COD for sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$) was 89.5% at 1.7 g/L, sodium hypochlorite ($NaOCl$) was 84.6 % at 2.0 g/L and calcium hypochlorite [$Ca(OCl)_2$] was 72 % at 2.0 g/L respectively as shown in figure 3(e). As the dosage of potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) was 2.4 g/L, the maximum removal rate of COD for sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$) was 91.2 % at 0.8 g/L, sodium hypochlorite ($NaOCl$) was 82.5 % at 2.0 g/L and calcium hypochlorite [$Ca(OCl)_2$] was 81.7 % at 1.4 g/L respectively. The results of the experiment were shown in figure 3(f). As can be seen from the figure 3(a) to (f), we observed that the composition effect of potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) and sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$) has a better removal rate and greater reaction efficiency. The percentage removal of COD with these oxidants composition [potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) and sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$)] was much greater than other oxidants composition. The best dosage was 1.6 g/L for potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) and 0.8 g/L for sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$). The composition effect of double oxidants gave a better performance on the removal of chemical oxygen demand (COD) from the pesticide wastewater sample. The reaction time and treatment cost also reduced effectively by using these new composite COD remover as compared with other traditional oxidants. The mechanism of degradation of organic pollutants in wastewater by potassium ferrate is mainly to destroy the key positions and functional groups in macromolecular organic matter by its strong oxidation, so that it can be degraded into small molecules that are easy to carry out biochemical reactions (J.-Q. Jiang & Lloyd, 2002; Jia Qian Jiang et al., 2006).

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Figure 3 The composition effect of double oxidants on the rate of COD removal

3.3 Effect of composition of coupling oxidant and flocculants on the rate of COD removal

As the results of the above experimental data, the composition effect of coupling oxidant and flocculants were also studied for this experiment. Figure 4 shows the composition effect of coupling oxidant and flocculants on the rate of COD removal. Potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) was

chosen as the oxidant and poly-ferric sulfate (PFS) and poly-aluminium ferric silicate (PSAF) were chosen as flocculants for the coupling composition reaction. In this experiment, the dosages of potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) were 1.4 g, 1.6 g, 1.8 g, 2.0 g and 2.4 g/L for each experiment and poly-ferric sulfate (PFS) and poly-aluminium ferric silicate (PSAF) were set as 0.1 g, 0.2 g, 0.3 g, 0.4 g, 0.5 g and 0.6 g/L respectively. According to the figure 4(a) and (b), the best removal effect was given the coupling composition of potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) and poly-ferric sulfate (PFS). The results of the removal rate did not have much difference between PFS and PSAF. The maximum removal rate was 91.7 % for 0.5 g of PFS and 91.2 % for 0.4 g of PSAF. The optimum dosage of coupling composition of potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) was found that 2.0 g for poly-ferric sulfate (PFS) and 1.6 g for poly-aluminium ferric silicate (PSAF). Poly-ferric sulfate (PFS) is an inorganic polymer flocculants that widely used in water and wastewater treatment. PFS displays a remarkable properties in the removal of turbidity, chemical oxygen demand (COD), biological oxygen demand (BOD) and color, compared to other traditional flocculants. Moreover, it has the characteristic of less dosage, good purification effect of wastewater and fast sedimentation effect in the reaction. PFS shows a good result in composition with potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) as compared with different dosages in this experiment (Hendrich et al., 2001; Liu, He, Li, & Wang, 2013). The composition effect of potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) and poly-ferric sulfate (PFS) on the pesticide wastewater sample was clearly seen in the figure 4(a). The reaction activity of poly-ferric sulfate (PFS) has improved by coupling with potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4).

(a)

(b)

Figure 4 The composition effect of coupling oxidant and flocculants (a) PFS (b) PSAF on the rate of COD removal

3.4 Effect of reaction time on the rate of COD removal

According to the results from the above experimental data, we selected the best ratio of the each new composite COD remover and assigned the formula numbers for comparing the removal efficiency on the using raw wastewater sample by different experimental conditions. We assigned the formula numbers R-1 for potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) and sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$) composite, R-2 for potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) and sodium hypochlorite ($NaOCl$) composite, R-3 for potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) and poly-ferric sulfate (PFS) composite, R-4 for potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) and poly-aluminium ferric silicate (PSAF) composite, and R-5 for commercial COD remover from Shanxi province. In this experiment, potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) and calcium hypochlorite [$Ca(OCl)_2$] composite did not selected for the treatment because the removal efficiency was poor for the using raw wastewater sample. Figure 5 shows the effect of reaction time on the rate of COD removal. The experiments were made at the reaction temperature $40^\circ C$ and the pH of raw wastewater was maintained. The experiments were also carried out at the best dosages of each COD removers and the comparable COD remover was set as 1.6 g/L. The reaction time will influence on the rate of COD removal in some extent. As the results from the figure 5,

the reaction time of 30 minutes shows the most obvious removal rate of COD from the raw wastewater sample. The removal rate of each COD removers in 30 minutes reaction time were 97.3 % for R-1, 89.5 % for R-2, 91.7 % for R-3, 91.2 % for R-4, and 80.9 % for R-5. When the reaction time reached to 40 minutes and above, the removal effect of each COD removers and the comparable commercial COD remover were gradually decreased. It was found that the prolong reaction time affected on the removal rate and lower the reaction rate of COD removers. The prepared composite COD remover (R-1) was more effective than the comparable commercial COD remover (R-5) for the removal of COD from the raw pesticide wastewater sample. Therefore, the prepared composite COD remover (R-1) was the effective and best remover for the reduction of chemical oxygen demand (COD).

Figure 5 Effect of reaction time on the rate of COD removal

3.5 Effect of pH on the rate of COD removal

The effects of pH on the rate of COD removal are shown in figure 6. The experiments were carried out at the best dosages of each COD removers with 30 minutes reaction time and pH varied from 4 to 10 as adjusted by sulphuric acid and sodium hydroxide solution. The reaction temperature was kept at 40°C. Pesticides are regularly created as neutral to weak alkaline or weak acids products. The pH of the pesticide solution can impact how long a pesticide molecule persists intact (Whitford, 2009). It was observed that the best removal rate for the most composite COD removers and the comparable commercial COD remover was achieved at pH 6. The maximum

removal rates of COD were 97.3 % for R-1 at pH 6, 89.5 % for R-2 at pH 5, 91.7 % for R-3 at pH 7, 91.2 % for R-4 at pH 6, and 80.9 % for R-5 at pH 6 respectively. It was found that the prepared composite COD removers R-1, R-4 and the comparable commercial COD remover R-5 worked very well in the acidic condition. The prepared composite COD remover R-3 was given the maximum removal rate at the neutral pH 7. The reaction efficiencies of the prepared COD removers lower when the pH of the wastewater sample reached to basic condition. The removal rate of COD was gradually decreased between the pH 8 and 10. At the neutral pH -7, the reaction rate was normal in condition. The organic pollutants that included in the wastewater sample were effectively reacted between the pH 4 and 6. According to the results from the figure 6, the prepared composite COD remover (R-1) has the good removal effect of chemical oxygen demand (COD) from the using raw wastewater sample as compared with the other composite COD removers and the comparable commercial COD remover.

Figure 6 Effect of pH on the rate of COD removal

3.6 Effect of reaction temperature on the rate of COD removal

The effects of reaction temperature on the rate of COD removal are shown in figure 7. The experiments were carried out at the best dosages of each COD removers with 30 minutes reaction time and pH of the wastewater was maintained. As can be seen from the figure 7, the maximum removal rate was observed at the 40°C of reaction temperature. The removal rate of COD cannot be greatly improved by increasing the temperature above 50°C. The possible reason

is that the quenching reaction between the free radicals was more likely to occur at high temperature, and the reaction ability was limited by the amount of free radicals consumed. The best removal rate of composite COD removers and the comparable commercial COD remover were 97.3 % for R-1, 89.5 % for R-2, 91.7 % for R-3, 91.2 % for R-4, and 80.9 % for R-5 respectively. It was also found that the reaction of the prepared composite COD remover with the wastewater sample lower when the reaction temperature was increased to the highest condition. The prepared composite COD remover (R-1) was effectively reduced the chemical oxygen demand (COD) in the pesticide wastewater sample. The reaction efficiency of the comparable commercial COD remover was lower than the prepared composite COD remover (R-1). The prepared composite COD remover (R-1) reduced the chemical oxygen demand (COD) to the acceptable limit. Therefore, it can be concluded that the prepared composite COD remover (R-1) is the suitable to use for the removal of COD from the raw wastewater sample.

Figure 7 Effect of reaction temperature on the rate of COD removal

3.7 Comparison of technical and economic indexes between prepared composite COD remover and commercial COD remover

Based on the above experimental data and results, the comparable cost and reaction efficiency of the prepared composite COD removers and the commercial COD remover were shown in table (2). The experiments were made at the reaction temperature 40°C and the pH of raw wastewater was maintained. The experiments were also carried out at the best dosages of each

COD removers and the comparable COD remover was set as 1.6 g/L. The new composite COD remover (R-1) is the best and cost-effective among other removers as the comparable results from the table 2. Moreover, the new composite COD remover (R-1) can effectively reduce the COD from the raw pesticide wastewater sample. The reaction efficiency was great in the using wastewater sample. The removal rate of COD increased by more than 16 % as to compare with the commercial COD remover. The time of treatment can also be greatly reduced by using these prepared composite COD remover. Therefore, the best prepared composite COD remover is the formula number R-1 [potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) and sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$)] composite COD remover.

Table 2 Comparison between prepared composite COD remover and commercial COD remover

Sr.No.	Formula Number	Rate of COD removal (%)	Experimental cost per ton of wastewater (USD)
1.	R-1	97.3 %	0.86
2.	R-2	89.5 %	0.89
3.	R-3	91.7 %	0.95
4.	R-4	91.2 %	1.05
5.	R-5*	80.9 %	1.68

* The commercial COD remover from Shanxi province

3.8 Analysis on the action mechanism of the COD remover

In this study, we prepared the composite COD remover by using double oxidants composition method and coupling oxidant and flocculants composition method. The composite COD remover made by double oxidants composition method gave a better reaction and removal efficiency for the raw wastewater. The treatment that using only one oxidant or flocculants occurs the slow reaction rate and low removal rate of organic matter from the wastewater sample. A new different methods for decontamination and removal of organic and inorganic pollutants from water and wastewater in developing oxidation process is the usage of iron in a valence of +6 state as FeO_4^{2-} [Fe (VI)] (Bandala et al., 2009; Ria, Seelawut, Khemarath, & Sharma, 2007; V. K. Sharma, 2007). Ferrate (VI) ion that included in the prepared composite COD remover is an active oxidant in aqueous medium as proposed by their reduction capabilities in the following reactions (1) and (2) (Lee, Cho, Kim, & Yoon, 2004; Virender K Sharma et al., 2005).

During the process of oxidation, ferrate (VI) ion will partially disintegrate and oxidize organic and inorganic pollutants, produce coagulants in an individual dosing and mixing unit process and eliminate suspended/colloidal particulate matters and heavy metals from the treated water. Therefore, we prepared the composite COD remover on the basis of potassium ferrate (Jia-Qian & Barry, 2002; J.-Q. Jiang, 2014; J Q Jiang, 2007; Ria et al., 2007). Moreover, potassium ferrate produces oxygen and iron hydroxide in an aqueous solution. Potassium ferrate that included in the composite COD remover can not only oxidize and degrade organic pollutants in the wastewater sample and but also generate iron hydroxide to play a certain treatment effect. Therefore, it can mainly support the prepared composite COD remover to destroy the key positions and functional groups in macromolecular organic matters that included in the wastewater sample. The strong oxidation effect of the prepared composite COD remover can be degraded the complex pollutants into small molecules that are convenient to perform the biochemical reactions. Under acidic conditions, the redox potential of potassium ferrate is 2.2 V, while it decreases to 0.72 V under alkaline conditions. It can be regarded that potassium ferrate is more oxidized under acidic conditions than alkaline conditions. When the composite COD remover is in a strong acidic condition with a pH of 4, although it has a strong oxidation ability, high concentration of H^+ will affect the stability of potassium ferrate that enable it to decompose quickly in a rapid treatment time to produce Fe^{3+} ion for the reaction, thereby weakening the oxidation effect of the prepared COD remover. Therefore, the prepared COD remover can works very well in the pH of 6. Under the alkaline conditions, the redox potential of the COD remover is low, so the water soluble organic matter and reducing matter is difficult to be effectively removed. It leads to the removal rate of COD from the wastewater sample gradually reduce in the treatment (Bandala et al., 2009; J.-Q. Jiang, 2014; J.-Q. Jiang & Lloyd, 2002; J Q Jiang, 2007; Jia Qian Jiang et al., 2006; Shah, Chauhan, & Galgale, 2012; Virender K. Sharma, 2002; V. K. Sharma, 2007; Zhang, Xu, Cheng, & Li, 2007).

Additionally, the prepared composite COD remover was rapidly mixed with the wastewater sample after the 15 minutes reaction time at the 150 rpm mixing. The degradation of the composite COD remover was followed by the markedly change in colour of the treated wastewater sample. Some yellowish precipitates obvious at the bottom of the beaker shows the

degradation effect of the prepared COD remover. So, the remover gave a good reaction performance in the wastewater sample and reduces the time of reaction for the treatment. The double oxidants composition method is simple and implementable in practice. The composition effect of potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) and sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$) creates more oxidation stability and potential during the treatment of the wastewater sample. The requirement of complicated wastewater treatment facilities can also be reduced during the treatment. The prepared composite COD remover cannot create the secondary pollution problems as compared with other commercial COD remover (Hammer, 1986; Jia Qian Jiang et al., 2006; Li, Li, & Graham, 2005; Song & Ma, 2013). For that reason, the usage of the prepared COD remover provides maximum removal efficiency for COD, when compared with other oxidants and commercial COD remover that it can be applied as a unique reaction efficiency and cost-effective composite COD remover for the removal of chemical oxygen demand (COD) from the pesticide wastewater sample.

4. Conclusion

The experimental study showed that the prepared composite COD remover had effective reaction performance for the removal of chemical oxygen demand (COD) from the raw pesticide industrial wastewater sample. From all of the results it was regarded that the maximum percentage reduction of COD from the using raw wastewater sample was obtained 97.3 % by using the new composite COD remover R-1 (potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) and sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$) composite COD remover at the pH of 6, reaction temperature 40°C, and 30 minutes reaction time. The removal rate of COD increased by more than 16% as compared with the commercial COD remover. The cost of the treatment per ton of wastewater was 0.86 USD. The treatment cost decreased by more than 6 % as to compare with the commercial COD remover. Therefore, the formula number R-1 (potassium ferrate (K_2FeO_4) and sodium chlorate ($NaClO_3$) composite COD remover had the significance unique performance, cost-effective and greatly reduce the chemical oxygen demand (COD).

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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